

Highly selective dual-band interdigital bandpass filter for C-band applications

Zakaria El Ouadi¹, Asma Khabba¹, Jamal Amadid¹, Saida Ibnyaich¹, Abdelouhab Zeroual¹,
Tole Sutikno²

¹Instrumentation, Signals and Physical Systems (I2SP) Team, Department of Physics, Faculty of Sciences Semlalia, Cadi Ayyad University, Marrakesh, Morocco

²Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Industrial Technology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 11, 2023

Revised Nov 3, 2023

Accepted Dec 9, 2023

Keywords:

C-band
Dual-band
Interdigital bandpass filter
Microwave filters
Parallel-coupled lines

ABSTRACT

Miniaturization in the telecommunications field is deemed a current challenge and a critical demand in order to improve communication quality between the transmitter and the receiver while avoiding clutter issues. The main objective of this work is to design a miniature interdigital bandpass filter (IBF) using planar technology. The proposed bandpass filter is made up of three equidistant parallel-coupled lines carefully deposited on a small Rogers-5880 substrate possessing a full dimension of $10 \times 10 \times 1.6$ mm³, a relative permittivity $\epsilon_r=2.2$, and a loss tangen of 0.0009. The proposed IBF has been designed and simulated using the HFSS software, which is a simulator that studies the electromagnetic behavior of radio frequency structures using cutting-edge finite element solvers. The reached outcomes present good electrical performance in terms of insertion loss S_{21} , reflection coefficient S_{11} , voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR), and selectivity, making the proposed IBF suitable for integration in small electronic devices for C-band applications (4 GHz to 8 GHz).

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Asma Khabba

Instrumentation, Signals and Physical Systems (I2SP) Team, Department of Physics

Faculty of Sciences Semlalia, Cadi Ayyad University

Marrakesh, Morocco

Email: khabba.asma@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of telecommunication systems and the exponential growth in the number of users owning wireless communication devices have allowed the creation and innovation of several technologies to simplify the exchange of information between the transmitter and the receiver [1]. The communication is carried out via a wireless communication system made up of several electronic components, among them, filters are deemed a primordial part of modern telecommunication systems such as radars, satellites, and cell phones [2]. Generally, a filter is a linear physical system considered a two-port quadrupole. This system performs a signal processing operation to eliminate unwanted frequencies and let through useful ones [3]. Typically, microwave bandpass filters are used in the telecommunications field to select a suitable frequency band while attenuating all unwanted frequencies. Traditionally, microwave filters were designed separately with dielectric resonators and metallic cavities. These kinds of filters called volumic filters provide excellent electrical performance, but unfortunately, they are bulky, heavy, and expensive [4], [5].

Planar filters represent a mutation and a technological revolution that have enabled designers to integrate their filters in small electronic devices while preserving space for other communication system

components and avoiding congestion problems. A planar filter is composed of metal strips generally made of copper deposited on the upper face of an insulating substrate. These metallic strips called resonators are folded or coupled together to generate filtering functions [6]–[8]. Planar filters can be integrated with microstrip antennas and form single multifunctional devices capable of filtering and radiating which simplifies the communication chain and reduces interconnection loss [9]–[18]. In general, a microwave bandpass filter is considered a competitor if it meets the current trend's requirements which are compact size, high selectivity (high-quality factor), low insertion loss (close to 0 dB), low reflection coefficient (less than -10 dB), and affordable cost.

To date, a significant amount of research has been carried out to propose various planar bandpass filter designs. For instance, a planar interdigital bandpass filter was proposed in [19]. The simulated results showed an acceptable insertion loss value ($S_{21} = -1$ dB), however, a poor quality factor was achieved ($Q=2.7$) and the structure was deposited on the top face of a sizeable Rogers RO4003C substrate ($>10 \times 10$ mm²). In Abdulkareem *et al.* [20], a fan-shaped microstrip bandpass filter was suggested. The simulated results are satisfying in term of reflection coefficient ($S_{11} < -10$ dB), but a slightly high insertion loss ($S_{21} = -1.377$ dB) was obtained and the structure was implemented on a large RT/Duroid 6010.2 dielectric substrate (12×12 mm²). A new compact bandpass filter using u-shaped resonators and distance gain size (DGZ) method was presented in [21], the simulated results show a good insertion loss value (-0.429 dB). However, a degraded quality factor was provided ($Q=6.97$) and the structure was deposited on a bulky RO4003C substrate (43.5×34.3 mm²). In Juma'a *et al.* [22], a two square open loop resonators were designed and implemented on a Rogers RT5880 substrate. The obtained results were good in terms of insertion loss ($S_{21} < -1$ dB) and reflection coefficient ($S_{11} < -30$ dB), but there is an issue of the large size (24.2×27 mm²). Another bandpass filter consisting of parallel coupled lines was suggested in [23]. Although the simulated insertion loss was good ($S_{21} = -0.6$ dB), the structure was implemented on a slightly large Rogers RO4003C substrate (21.5×7.1 mm²). As seen in the previous cited works, all the proposed structures presented an issue of the size, some of them presented a low quality factor and a high insertion loss, which degrades the quality of the filter and makes it difficult to integrate with small electronic devices.

For this reason, a small and compact interdigital bandpass filter (IBF) is designed. The suggested structure is composed of three equidistant parallel coupled lines carefully deposited on a miniature Rogers 5880 substrate possessing a total dimension ($10 \times 10 \times 1.6$ mm³) relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r=2.2$, a loss tangent of 0.0009, and a thickness h equal to 1.6 mm. The compact structure and the brilliant performance reached by the suggested IBF prove its suitability for integration in wireless devices that support highly selective operation.

2. INTERDIGITAL BANDPASS FILTER

An interdigital band-pass filter is made up of a series of resonators with lengths equal to the quarter-wavelength guided in the substrate. These resonators are placed next to each other forming a distributive coupling. To resonate the quarter wave filter we need to connect one end to the ground and the other to an open circuit as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Topology of an n -pole filter with interdigitated quarter-wave resonators

3. PROPOSED INTERDIGITAL BANDPASS FILTER

Figure 2 exhibits the proposed design structure. The front side consists of a symmetrical microstrip transmission line powered from both sides by an impedance line of 50Ω . Three lines of equal length and equidistant spacing are deposited on the upper face of Rogers's dielectric substrate as shown in Figure 2(a). Figure 2(b) shows the rear side of the proposed structure containing a copper ground plane with a rectangular slot deposited under the substrate to improve the electrical performance of the proposed IBF.

Figure 2. Structure of the suggested IBF: (a) front side and (b) rear side

The following theoretical equations are used to calculate the resonator's full dimension [24]. The resonator's width W_r is obtained using the following equation:

$$\frac{W_r}{h} = \frac{8 \left(\frac{7\epsilon_r + 4}{11\epsilon_r} A + \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{0.81\epsilon_r} \right)^{0.5}}{A} \quad (1)$$

Where,

$$A = \exp \left(\frac{z_0}{42.4} \sqrt{\epsilon_r + 1} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

Knowing that z_0 is the characteristic impedance of the line equal to 50Ω . The resonator's length L_r is obtained using the following equation.

$$L_r = \frac{\lambda_g}{4} - \Delta L \quad (3)$$

Where ΔL represents the effective length of the resonator due to the overflow effect, and λ_g indicates the substrate's guided wavelength given by:

$$\lambda_g = \frac{\lambda_0}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{reff}}}} \quad (4)$$

Knowing that λ_0 denotes the wavelength in free space at the center frequency f_0 , and the effective relative permittivity provided by the microstrip synthesis denoted as ϵ_{reff} .

$$\epsilon_{\text{reff}} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left[1 + 12 \frac{h}{W_r} \right]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

The IBF dimensions are assembled in Table 1.

Parameters	Dimensions (mm)	Parameters	Dimensions (mm)
L_s	10	W_s	10
L_{f1}	3	L_{f2}	3
L_r	8	W_r	1
l_c	1	W_c	8
L_g	10	W_g	10

4. RESULTS AND DESCUSSION

The design was done using the HFSS software which is a simulator that studies the electromagnetic behavior of radio frequency structures using cutting-edge finite element solvers. The structure was first deposited on two different types of substrate which are FR4 epoxy and Rogers-5880, to see the effect of each one.

4.1. Simulated reflection and transmission coefficients for Rogers-58880 and FR4 epoxy substrates

It is clearly remarked in Figure 3 that the structure of the interdigital filter deposited on the upper face of the Rogers 5880 substrate has much greater electrical performance than that of the FR4 epoxy substrate. Using the Rogers substrate, a dual-band IBF has been achieved, as a result, a double resonance frequency is attained, whereas using the FR4 epoxy, only a single band with a single resonance frequency was obtained. As observed in the following figure, poor reflection and transmission coefficients (S_{11}) or (S_{21}) were obtained for the FR4 epoxy substrate $S_{11} \geq -20$ dB and $S_{21} \leq -2$ dB resulting in a high insertion loss value which is unpreferred for planar technology design.

Figure 3. Reflection and transmission coefficients versus frequency for FR4 epoxy and Rogers-5880 substrates

4.2. Details of chosen results

Figure 4 depicts the electrical performance of the IBF structure deposited on the upper side of the Rogers-5880 substrate. As remarked in this figure, the filtering operation is performed on two bands belonging to the C band with a reflection coefficient value $S_{11} < -20$ dB for both resonant frequencies 6.17 GHz and 7.16 GHz, which proves a good impedance matching and implies that 90% of the power is transmitted while 10% is reflected due to the discontinuity effect.

Figure 4. Reflection and transmission coefficients versus frequency

It is also observed that the filter provides a very good band rejection of less than -50 dB with an insertion loss value of S_{21} equal to -0.13 dB and -0.11 dB at 6.17 GHz and 7.16 GHz, respectively. The proposed IBF has two -3 dB bandwidths equal to 230 MHz and 560 MHz, respectively. Knowing that the two resonance frequencies are 6.17 and 7.16, the quality factor (Q) can be calculated for each band and it can be deduced that the filter is highly selective for the first frequency band and has good selectivity for the second one. The quality factor can be calculated using the following equation where f_r is the resonant frequency for each frequency band.

$$Q = \frac{f_r}{-3dB \text{ Bandwidth}} \quad (6)$$

4.3. Voltage standing wave ratio

Figure 5 presents the simulated voltage standing wave ratio versus frequency for the dual-band IBF. As seen in this figure, the IBF has a low voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) equal to 1.73 and 0.15 at the resonance frequencies 6.17 GHz and 7.16 GHz, respectively. This confirms the previously obtained results and that the IBF has a good impedance match with a low number of reflected waves which is desirable for the planar technology design.

Figure 5. Voltage standing wave ratio versus frequency for the dual-band IBF

4.4. Distributed current density

Figures 6(a) and 6(b) depict the distribution of current density over the IBF's surface at the resonant frequency of 6.17 GHz and 7.16 GHz, respectively. It can be observed in both figures that all the colors on the scale are distributed over the surface of the three coupled resonators. The blue color indicates a weaker coupling effect, whereas the red color represents a stronger one. It is also remarked that the current intensity is much higher at the resonance frequency of 7.16 GHz compared to that obtained at the frequency of 6.17 GHz which is compatible with the previous results.

Figure 6. Distribution of current density: (a) at 6.17 GHz and (b) at 7.16 GHz

5. COMPARISON STUDY

Table 2 compares the performance and the characteristics of the proposed IBF with other recently proposed filters. Resonant frequency (fr), insertion loss ($In. Loss$), size, and quality factor (Q) were chosen as parameters for this comparison. It can be deduced that the proposed IBF has a small and compact size compared to other designed filters; it is also very selective and has the lowest insertion loss values, making it competitive and suitable for integration in small electronic devices.

Table 2. Comparison study

References	fr (GHz)	Q	$In. Loss$ (dB)	Size (mm ²)
[19]	6.31	2.7	-1	>10×10
[20]	3.41/ 6.14	–	-0.7/ -1.377	12×12
[21]	2.4	6.97	-0.429	43.5×34.3
[25]	1.93/ 2.41	6.89/ 5.02	-0.6/ -0.5	28.3×21.7
[26]	2.45/ 5.8	8.16/ 14.5	-1.3/ -2.2	–
[27]	2.4	20	-0.91	22×22
Proposed IBF	6.17/ 7.16	26.82/ 12.78	-0.13/ -0.11	10×10

6. CONCLUSION

A compact interdigital bandpass filter with planar technology approach was suggested in this paper. The proposed design has a small size 10×10 (mm²) and performs very well in terms of insertion loss (-0.13/-0.11) dB and reflection coefficient $S_{11} < -20$ dB for both resonant frequencies 6.17 GHz and 7.16 GHz, respectively. The proposed IBF provides a good rejection band less than -50 dB and proves a high selectivity making it competitive and suitable for integration with small electronic devices, such as microstrip antennas operating for C-band (4 GHz to 8 GHz) applications. This integration will result in a single multifunctional device able of radiating and filtering. Consequently, this will reduce the interconnection loss and simplify the wireless communication chain complexity.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Kumar, *Wireless Communication-the fundamental and advanced concepts*. 2015, doi: 10.1201/9781003340058.
- [2] N. O. Parchin, Y. I. A. Al-Yasir, and R. A. Abd-Alhameed, "Microwave/RF components for 5G front-end systems," *Avid Science* 2019.
- [3] N. Krishna V and K. G. Padmasine, "A review on microwave band pass filters: Materials and design optimization techniques for wireless communication systems," *Materials Science in Semiconductor Processing*, vol. 154, p. 107181, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.mssp.2022.107181.
- [4] K. Bi, X. Wang, Y. Hao, M. Lei, G. Dong, and J. Zhou, "Wideband slot-coupled dielectric resonator-based filter," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 785, pp. 1264–1269, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.01.286.
- [5] A. Pons-Abenza, A. Alvarez-Melcon, F. D. Quesada-Pereira, and L. Arche-Andradas, "Frequency Correction Design Technique for Additive Manufactured Cavity Filters," in *2018 48th European Microwave Conference, EuMC 2018*, IEEE, Sep. 2018, pp. 288–291, doi: 10.23919/EuMC.2018.8541362.
- [6] Z. El Ouadi, J. Amadid, A. Khabba, A. El Yassini, S. Ibnyaich, and A. Zeroual, "Three Folded U -Shaped Resonators with Good Harmonics Suppression for S-Band Radar Applications," in *Proceedings - 2022 5th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technologies and Networking, CommNet 2022*, IEEE, Dec. 2022, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/CommNet56067.2022.9993877.
- [7] S. C. Tang, P. C. Chu, J. T. Kuo, L. K. Wu, and C. H. Lin, "Compact Microstrip Wideband Cross-Coupled Inline Bandpass Filters With Miniaturized Stepped-Impedance Resonators (SIRs)," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 21328–21335, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3153710.
- [8] A. Slimani, S. Das, W. A. E. Ali, A. El Alami, S. D. Bennani, and M. Jorio, "Second order microstrip bandpass filter design based on square resonator for 5G sub-6 GHz band," *Journal of Instrumentation*, vol. 17, no. 7, 2022, doi: 10.1088/1748-0221/17/07/P07002.
- [9] Z. El Ouadi, A. Khabba, J. Amadid, A. El Yassini, S. Ibnyaich, and A. Zeroual, "Low-Cost Compact Hairpin Filter Integrated with a Diamond Antenna for Wireless and 5G Sub-6 GHz Applications," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 131, no. 2, pp. 921–939, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11277-023-10461-w.
- [10] P. Pal, R. Sinha, and S. K. Mahto, "A Compact Wideband Circularly Polarized Planar Filtenna Using Synthesis Technique for 5 GHz WLAN Application," *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, vol. 148, p. 154180, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.aeu.2022.154180.
- [11] Z. El Ouadi, J. Amadid, A. Khabba, A. El Yassini, S. Ibnyaich, and A. Zeroual, "Compact Microstrip Filtenna Designed For Wireless Local Area Network Applications," in *2022 International Conference on Decision Aid Sciences and Applications, DASA 2022*, IEEE, Mar. 2022, pp. 1593–1597, doi: 10.1109/DASA54658.2022.9765235.
- [12] Z. A. Abdul Hassain, A. A. AL-Behadili, and A. R. Azeez, "First order parallel coupled BPF with wideband rejection based on SRR and CSRR," *Telkonnika (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 2704–2712, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v17i6.10790.
- [13] C. Mohammed, B. Fatima, and D. Mehdi, "A novel cross-coupled microstrip bandpass filter with hairpin-DGS resonators using coupling matrix technique," *Telkonnika (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 465–475, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.V18I1.12447.
- [14] Y. Luo, J. Yu, Y. Cheng, F. Chen, and H. Luo, "A compact microwave bandpass filter based on spoof surface plasmon polariton and substrate integrated plasmonic waveguide structures," *Applied Physics A: Materials Science and Processing*, vol. 128, no. 2,

Highly selective dual-band interdigital bandpass filter for C-band applications (Zakaria El Ouadi)

- p. 97, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s00339-021-05250-w.
- [15] R. D. Bharathi, J. E. Yamini, A. Evangeline, and D. Badri Narayanan, "Design and analysis of interdigital microstrip bandpass filter for centre frequency 2.4 GHz," in *ICONSTEM 2017 - Proceedings: 3rd IEEE International Conference on Science Technology, Engineering and Management*, IEEE, Mar. 2017, pp. 930–933, doi: 10.1109/ICONSTEM.2017.8261339.
- [16] Y. I. A. Al-Yasir, N. O. Parchin, R. A. Abd-Alhameed, A. M. Abdulkhaleq, and J. M. Noras, "Recent progress in the design of 4G/5G reconfigurable filters," *Electronics (Switzerland)*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 114, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3390/electronics8010114.
- [17] M. Challal, K. Hocine, and A. Mermoul, "A Novel Design of Compact Dual-Band Bandpass Filter for Wireless Communication Systems," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 109, no. 3, pp. 1713–1726, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s11277-019-06648-9.
- [18] Y. Xu, Z. Liu, S. Wang, W. Tang, and J. Chen, "Design of a Multilayer Dual-Band Balanced Bandpass Filter on a Circular Patch Resonator," *Frontiers in Physics*, vol. 9, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.3389/fphy.2021.709150.
- [19] S. Saleh, W. Ismail, I. S. Zainal Abidin, and M. H. Jamaluddin, "5G Hairpin and Interdigital Bandpass Filters," *International Journal of Integrated Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 71–79, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.30880/ijie.2020.12.06.009.
- [20] S. F. Abdulkareem, Z. Faydh, and D. H. Al-Nuaimi, "Investigation of dualband fan-shaped microstrip bandpass filter," *Telkommika (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 229–234, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.V19I1.16507.
- [21] A. Belmajdoub, A. Boutejdar, A. El Alami, S. D. Bennani, and M. Jorio, "Design and optimization of a new compact 2.4 GHz-bandpass filter using DGS technique and U-shaped resonators for WLAN applications," *Telkommika (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 1081–1089, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.V17I3.10913.
- [22] F. K. Juma'a, A. I. Al-Mayoof, A. A. Abdalhameed, F. M. Alnahwi, Y. I. A. Al-Yasir, and R. A. Abd-Alhameed, "Design and Implementation of a Miniaturized Filtering Antenna for 5G Mid-Band Applications," *Electronics (Switzerland)*, vol. 11, no. 19, p. 2979, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.3390/electronics11192979.
- [23] A. Basheer, H. Abdulhussein, H. Al-Saedi, and J. K. Ali, "Design of Bandpass Filter for 5G Applications with High-selectivity and Wide Band Rejection," in *Al-Muthanna 2nd International Conference on Engineering Science and Technology, MICEST 2022 - Proceedings*, IEEE, Mar. 2022, pp. 179–183, doi: 10.1109/MICEST54286.2022.9790185.
- [24] D. M. Pozar, *Microwave Engineering*. John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
- [25] K. Saini, A. Kumar, K. S. Rathore, and M. Ali, "Bandpass Filter with Interdigital Capacitor in Open Loop Resonator for Wimax, RF-MEMS, and PCS Applications," *International Journal of Advances in Microwave Technology*, vol. 05, no. 01, pp. 223–226, 2020, doi: 10.32452/ijamt.2020.223226.
- [26] M. Danaeian, A. R. Moznebi, and K. Afrooz, "Super compact dual-band substrate integrated waveguide filters and filtering power dividers based on evanescent-mode technique," *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, vol. 125, p. 153348, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.aeue.2020.153348.
- [27] S. Karthie and S. Salivahanan, "Fractally slotted patch resonator based compact dual-mode microstrip bandpass filter for Wireless LAN applications," *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, vol. 107, pp. 264–274, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.aeue.2019.05.037.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Zakaria El Ouadi received a B.S. degree in Electronics in 2018 from the Cadi Ayyad University, Marrakech, Morocco. In 2020, he received the M.S. degree in Control, Industrial Computer, Signals, and Physical Systems from Cadi Ayyad University of Marrakesh, Morocco. He is currently a Ph.D. student in Telecommunications Engineering at the Cadi Ayyad University of Marrakesh, Morocco. His main research interest includes the filter nozzle design for 5G applications. He can be contacted at email: zakaria.elouadi@edu.uca.ac.ma.

Asma Khabba received the B.S. in Physics and the Master degree in Control, Industrial Computing, Signals and Systems in 2015 and 2017 respectively from Cadi Ayyad University. She is currently pursuing her studies to accomplish the Ph.D. degree in Telecommunication and Signal Processing at Cady Ayyad University, Marrakech, Morocco. Her research interests include 5G antenna, microwave/millimeter wave antenna, phased array and MIMO antenna. She can be contacted at email: asma.khabba@edu.uca.ac.ma.

Jamal Amadid got the B.S. in Physics and the M.S. degree in Control, Industrial Computing, Signals and Systems from Cadi Ayyad University in 2016 and 2019 respectively. Currently, he is continuing his study to complete the Ph.D. degree. His main research interests are: massive-MIMO network, channel estimation for spatial correlated channels, pilot contamination and the cell-free massive-MIMO in the 5G wireless communications system. He can be contacted at email: jamal.amadid@edu.uca.ac.ma.

Saida Ibnyaich is currently a professor at Cadi Ayyad University, Marrakesh, Morocco. She received the bachelor degree in Technical Sciences, the master degree in Electrical Engineering, Power Electronics, and Industrial Control, and the PhD degree in Computing and Telecommunication in 2002, 2005, and 2013, respectively, from Cadi Ayyad University. Her research interests include telecommunications, microwaves, millimeter waves, PIFA antennas, and patch antennas. She can be contacted at email: s.ibnyaich@uca.ac.ma.

Abdelouhab Zeroual is a professor of Telecommunication Systems and Signal Processing. He is the head of the Instrumentation, Signals, and Systems Team at the Faculty of Sciences Semlalia, Cadi Ayyad University in Marrakesh, Morocco. He received his Ph.D. degree in 1995 from Cadi Ayyad University. He supervises several research projects and serves as a reviewer for a number of international journals. His research interests include instrumentation, solar energy, signal processing, and wireless communications. He has published more than 140 conference papers and more than 60 journal papers. He can be contacted at email: zeroual@edu.uca.ac.ma.

Tole Sutikno is currently employed as a lecturer in the Electrical Engineering Department at Universitas Ahmad Dahlan (UAD), which is located in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. In 1999, 2004, and 2016, he graduated with a Bachelor of Engineering from Universitas Diponegoro, a Master of Engineering from Universitas Gadjah Mada, and a Doctor of Philosophy in Electrical Engineering from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. All three degrees are in the field of electrical engineering. Since July 2023, he has been a full Professor at Universitas Ahmad Dahlan in Yogyakarta, Indonesia, after previously serving as an Associate Professor since June 2008. His research interests include the areas of digital design, industrial applications, industrial electronics, industrial informatics, power electronics, motor drives, renewable energy, FPGA applications, embedded systems, artificial intelligence, intelligent control, digital libraries, and information technology. He can be contacted at email: tole@te.uad.ac.id.